

Telecoms Industry and Money - A Path Ahead

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Abstract— This paper identifies the problems that Telco industry faces, proposes a long-term view and the pathway to stem this race to commoditization. In our opinion network operators need to create divergent sources of revenue. We recommend that in the long-term solution for the Telco industry to move to a platform-base ecosystem where 3rd parties can provide solutions for their respective industries. And the first step to get there is data driven market segmentation.

Keywords—ROI; 6G; Monetization; 5G-Slicing; Market segmentation; Ecosystems

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently operators compete to gather a higher share of the market from *other* operators, typically, by undercutting subscription costs resulting in a race to commoditization. This commoditization has led to various finance driven structural changes in the Telco market landscape - market consolidation, disaggregation of Telcos into InfraCo/NetCo/ServCo and growth in ownership of CSPs by financial investors. Most of this activity seems to be focused on cutting costs and realizing scale by consolidation, and not on growing the size of the market itself. We recommend a long-term view of platform play that has the possibility to realize revenues from markets where the telco industry has no expertise. The first step is creating market segments to realize the existing value in the market. We first look at the current state of the telecommunication industry.

A. Current State of Telco

In different markets 5G has different maturity. Most have deployed 5G NSA (Non-Standalone Access) to focus on the eMBB segment. To reach the potential of 5G, operators need to transfer from NSA to SA (Stand Alone, or 5G core). However, most have yet to recover the cost of their NSA investments and don't feel confident moving to SA. 5G SA offers monetization benefits such as radio boosts, fixed wireless access (FWA), vertical and industrial support via private networks and network slicing, followed by 5G advanced capabilities such as immersive experience, edge compute, RedCap, NTN, L4S support. Central Asia, India and North America are markets that lead the 5G journey, while the rest of the world is following.

B. Learnings From 5G

First phase is the 5G roll out allowed for eMBB subscription monetization moving from 4G to 5G subscriptions. Then early market movers focused on business cases such as: Enterprise, FWA, & eMBB Premium. FWA considered to be one of the top cases for standalone deployments especially in markets with large geographic coverage. The enterprise segment with private wireless and network slicing has a huge global market most of

Figure 1. Problems to monetize the telco

which has thus remained under realized outside Asia. The success of the enterprise market is thus far based on the successful realization of scale via slicing of the public network. The current efforts to take further advantages of the 5G capabilities are via monetization of API exposure. Noticeable, in conjunction with access technologies a platform play has emerged enable further monetization possibilities. Platforms emerging are AI-RAN [2], Edge support, API platforms including aggregators [3], and more important digitalization platforms for vertical/industrial segments.

II. PROBLEMS FACING TELCO INDUSTRY

The problem is largely cultural - the Telco industry holding on to its traditional processes in the face of softwarization. While the traditional processes have been successful and will stay important for rolling out new (radio) hardware solutions that are important to address the scale of deployment, these are not applicable to software. The failure to apply different processes to hardware aspects vs monetizable software features is in our opinion at the root cause of the loss of various monetization opportunities that have instead gone to the OTT providers. Three main issues are shown in Figure 1 are as follows.

A. Problem 1: Time to Market

Most typical telco industry use case and respective solutions are first discussed internally in companies, then finalized in standard bodies which takes about 1,5 to 2 years at the least. Then internal feasibility analysis for product implementation in the different product roadmaps happen. All in all, by the time this feature is implemented and fully supported it will be two to four years from conception to deployment. This procedure is incompatible and not competitive with the fast-moving software industry. Currently, this is the default for pretty much all features – this limits innovation as well as significantly slows down time to value of a new scenario and any valuable scenario is implemented by over-the-top players independently.

B. Problem 2: Inability to monetize new features

Newly developed innovative features are currently used to capture the additional market from other players and not for increasing or diversifying revenue. This leads to a race to the bottom and commoditization of the industry – which in turn tends to lower innovation and reduces appetite for risk taking.

C. Problem 3: Addressing B2B

5G network slicing was proposed to support business use-cases for industry and enterprises [1]. With NSA deployment slicing is not supported and hence the entire B2B idea did not take off. But even with SA deployments the industry barring certain markets has not been able to communicate the value of the network to the respective customers. We think the main problem has been trying to enter the new business areas - industry and enterprise - with a Telco hat on, and not from a perspective of the specific needs of industry or enterprise. For example, speaking about plug-n-play of radio infrastructure instead of lower down time during reorganization of the factory floor – even though they both refer to the same thing.

III. A VISION AND A FIRST STEP

We may need to move away from the current waterfall-based approach to an “platform play” supported by an ecosystem of service providers (SP) and their customers where any authorized SP can build solutions seamlessly for their own industry segment. In one line we need to:

“Develop a secure ecosystem that improves the time to market of new (3rd party) functionality and enables selling that functionality in a differentiated manner to the different customer segments in the ecosystem based on understanding of the needs of the particular customer segment utilizing the data collected from the user, network and other sources.”

This is a significant change from the way the industry is currently organized. Therefore, realizing such a vision is not easy especially given the financial, risk averse mood most of the telco industry is in. To get to an ecosystem the telco industry needs to attract sellers on the ecosystem – sellers in this case refers to 3rd party’s who can build solutions for their respective industries. They would only do so if they see a clear possibility to address their market segment. **The first step** would then be to ensure that sellers are able to sell their solutions over a telco owned platform. Here we revisit Problem 2: Inability to monetize new features.

The solutions lie in understanding our existing customers. For existing customers - Joel likes gaming, in fact he makes his living playing networked games. Phillipa on the other hand just needs to be able to receive her Whatsapp messages globally while traveling. Mark usually conducts various conference calls while driving. Joel is thus likely to be interested in gaming slices, Phillipa in global eMBB and Markus in high bandwidth conferencing slices directly to his car. The telco network has enough data on Joel, Phillipa and Mark to provide them tailored connectivity solution. This data driven creation of market segments is in our opinion the first step now.

Figure 2 The path ahead

Extending this to the future UEs, such as drones, mobile robots, and so forth will require different types of connectivity and the telco network will need to capability to provide them at scale using automation solutions based on data from the UEs and the network entities utilizing network slicing. Lastly, more innovative enablers like intent-based UE to network interfaces will enable an entirely new possibilities where the UEs owners are directly able to request services from the network.

Both automation and market segmentation require good understanding of data. While the importance of data has been understood before [4], what is different this time is the availability of AI-ML based enablers that will make the inference from this data more marketable. This can then be extended to newer use cases beyond market segmentation such as advertising based on UE locations or traffic and public transport planning based on predicted UE movements. Further, if we can integrate external data onto the platform a whole new set of scenarios can be enabled – some of which we are unable to imagine now. In our analysis there are still many questions that the Telco industry will need to answer about data management in 6G.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we looked at how creating data driven market segments as the first step towards monetization. Figure 2 shows the path that we think the evolution of telco industry may take from a monetization perspective. Some steps on this path may depend on the context of the market the operator is in. In most cases the FWA like access, particularly in geographical large or diverse countries has created/will create a new source of revenue for operators. Simultaneous, is the move to the private market. Both FWA and private networks can only be provided at scale using slicing implying an SA deployment. The initial use cases with the 5G APIs are taking off in the market and we feel should be enabled to grow to a full-fledged platform play. Lastly, we feel that as we move towards the next generation the monetization of telco networks will depend on correct capture and inference of data – data to create and capture value from new market segments, inference that creates new value and correlations with external data that create entirely new business opportunities that we can only partly foresee today.

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